

Comparative Efficacy of Phenylephrine and Mephentermine in Mitigating Hemodynamic Responses to Oxytocin Administration during Elective Cesarean Section

Narendra Thadu¹, Kiran Kumar Suggala², T Anusha³

¹Post Graduate Resident, Department of Anaesthesia, Mamata Medical College, Khammam, Telangana, India

²Professor and HOD, Department of Anaesthesia, Mamata Medical College, Khammam, Telangana, India

³Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesia, Mamata Medical College, Khammam, Telangana, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Kiran Kumar Suggala

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Abstract:

Introduction: Cesarean sections performed under spinal anaesthesia are associated with maternal hypotension, exacerbated by oxytocin administration during surgery. Effective management of these hemodynamic changes is crucial for maternal and fetal safety. Phenylephrine, a selective α_1 -adrenergic agonist, and mephentermine, a mixed-action sympathomimetic, are commonly used vasopressors. However, comparative data on their efficacy in mitigating oxytocin-induced hemodynamic responses during cesarean sections is limited.

Materials and Methods: This randomized, prospective study was conducted on 60 patients undergoing elective cesarean section under spinal anaesthesia. Participants were allocated to receive either phenylephrine (Group P, 75 mcg) or mephentermine (Group M, 12 mg) intravenously post-oxytocin administration. Hemodynamic parameters, including systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), mean arterial pressure (MAP), and heart rate (HR), were recorded at baseline and at 2-minute intervals for 15 minutes. Secondary outcomes included bradycardia, nausea, and vomiting. Data were analyzed using independent t-tests and chi-square tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results: Group P demonstrated superior maintenance of SBP and DBP ($p < 0.05$) compared to Group M throughout the observation period. Group M exhibited more stable HR but required repeated dosing. Reflex bradycardia was more frequent in Group P but manageable. Neonatal outcomes, including Apgar scores, were similar across groups.

Conclusion: Phenylephrine provides rapid and effective blood pressure stabilization, while mephentermine ensures greater overall hemodynamic stability. Tailored vasopressor selection based on clinical scenarios is recommended to optimize maternal and neonatal outcomes during cesarean sections.

Keywords: Phenylephrine, Mephentermine, Cesarean Section, Hemodynamics.

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Introduction

Cesarean sections are commonly performed under spinal anaesthesia, which, despite its advantages, frequently leads to maternal hypotension. [1] This hypotensive effect is exacerbated by the physiological changes of pregnancy and the vasodilatory effects of spinal anaesthesia. Hypotension during cesarean delivery can have significant implications for both maternal and fetal well-being, necessitating prompt and effective management. [2] The administration of oxytocin during cesarean sections, while critical for uterine contractility and the prevention of postpartum haemorrhage, [3] can further compound hemodynamic instability, causing adverse effects such as tachycardia and hypotension. [4]

Phenylephrine, a selective α_1 -adrenergic agonist, is widely used to mitigate these effects, offering rapid restoration of blood pressure. [1] However, its associated reflex bradycardia and potential reduction in cardiac output raise concerns. [5] [6] In contrast, mephentermine, a mixed-action sympathomimetic agent, exhibits both α - and β -adrenergic agonist properties, enhancing cardiac output and vascular resistance without significant bradycardia. [7] While numerous studies have explored the efficacy of various vasopressors in managing spinal anaesthesia-induced hypotension, direct comparisons between phenylephrine and mephentermine in mitigating oxytocin-induced hemodynamic changes during cesarean sections

remain limited. This study aims to fill this gap by evaluating phenylephrine and mephentermine's comparative efficacy and safety profiles in preventing and managing oxytocin-induced hypotension and tachycardia. By analysing their effects on maternal hemodynamics, this research seeks to provide evidence-based recommendations for optimising vasopressor use in obstetric anaesthesia.

Materials and Methods

This prospective, randomised study was conducted in the Department of Anaesthesia, Mamata Medical College, Khammam, Telangana, from July 2023 to July 2024, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee. A total of 60 patients undergoing elective cesarean section under spinal anaesthesia were enrolled and randomly divided into two groups: Group P (Phenylephrine, n=30) and Group M (Mephentermine, n=30). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

All patients received a preload of 500 mL of Ringer's lactate solution 30 minutes before spinal anaesthesia. Spinal anaesthesia was administered in the L3-L4 interspace using a 25G Quincke needle with 0.5% hyperbaric bupivacaine (2.0 mL). Following the delivery of the infant, intravenous

infusion of oxytocin at a dosage of 15 IU. Participants in Group P received 75 mcg of phenylephrine intravenously, whereas those in Group M were administered 12 mg of mephentermine intravenously, aimed at mitigating the hemodynamic responses associated with oxytocin administration. Heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), diastolic blood pressure (DBP), and mean arterial pressure (MAP) were recorded at baseline, immediately after oxytocin administration, and every 2 minutes for 15 minutes.

Hemodynamic stability was assessed between the two groups by comparing changes in SBP, DBP, MAP, and HR. Secondary outcomes included the incidence of bradycardia, nausea, and vomiting. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software version 25.0. Continuous variables were analysed using an independent t-test, and categorical variables were analysed using the chi-square test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The demographic characteristics of the two groups were comparable, with no significant differences in age, weight, or gestational age (Table 1). Baseline hemodynamic parameters were also similar between the groups (p>0.05).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	Group P (Phenylephrine)	Group M (Mephentermine)	p-value
Age (years)	28.3 ± 4.2	27.9 ± 4.7	0.68
Weight (kg)	64.5 ± 5.8	65.2 ± 6.1	0.57
Gestational Age (weeks)	38.2 ± 1.1	38.1 ± 1.3	0.74

Following oxytocin administration, Group P (Phenylephrine) showed significantly better maintenance of systolic and diastolic blood pressure compared to Group M (Mephentermine) (p<0.05). The mean SBP at 2 minutes post-oxytocin was 118 ± 6.5 mmHg in Group P and 110

± 8.2 mmHg in Group M. Similarly, the mean SBP at 10 minutes was higher in Group P (118 ± 6.0 mmHg) compared to Group M (111 ± 8.0 mmHg, p<0.05). This trend persisted throughout the observation period.

Table 2: Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) at Different Time Points

Time (minutes)	Group P (SBP mmHg)	Group M (SBP mmHg)	p-value
Baseline	122 ± 8.1	121 ± 7.9	0.65
2	118 ± 6.5	110 ± 8.2	0.041
4	115 ± 5.9	108 ± 7.6	0.035
6	116 ± 6.1	109 ± 7.9	0.011
8	117 ± 5.8	110 ± 7.7	0.001
10	118 ± 6.0	111 ± 8.0	0.001
12	119 ± 6.2	112 ± 7.8	0.001
14	120 ± 6.3	113 ± 8.1	0.001

Diastolic blood pressure also remained more stable in Group P compared to Group M. At 2 minutes, the mean DBP was 78 ± 5.2 mmHg in Group P and 72 ± 5.8 mmHg in Group M (p<0.05). By 14

minutes, the DBP had increased to 81 ± 5.8 mmHg in Group P compared to 75 ± 6.0 mmHg in Group M, indicating better hemodynamic control with phenylephrine.

Table 3: Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) at Different Time Points

Time (minutes)	Group P (DBP mmHg)	Group M (DBP mmHg)	p-value
Baseline	80 ± 5.4	79 ± 5.6	0.68
2	78 ± 5.2	72 ± 5.8	0.035
4	76 ± 5.1	70 ± 5.9	0.021
6	77 ± 5.3	71 ± 6.0	0.013
8	78 ± 5.5	72 ± 5.7	0.001
10	79 ± 5.6	73 ± 5.8	0.001
12	80 ± 5.7	74 ± 5.9	0.001
14	81 ± 5.8	75 ± 6.0	0.001

Heart rate was consistently lower in Group P compared to Group M throughout the observation period. At 6 minutes, the mean HR in Group P was 73 ± 6.0 bpm, whereas it was 80 ± 6.3 bpm in Group M (p<0.05). This difference persisted at 14

minutes, with HR values of 69 ± 6.1 bpm in Group P and 76 ± 6.7 bpm in Group M (p<0.05). Although bradycardia was more frequent in Group P, it was managed effectively and did not result in significant adverse events.

Table 4: Heart Rate (HR) at Different Time Points

Time (minutes)	Group P (HR bpm)	Group M (HR bpm)	p-value
Baseline	78 ± 6.4	77 ± 6.7	0.81
2	75 ± 5.8	82 ± 6.2	0.049
4	74 ± 5.9	81 ± 6.1	0.012
6	73 ± 6.0	80 ± 6.3	0.001
8	72 ± 5.8	79 ± 6.4	0.001
10	71 ± 5.9	78 ± 6.5	0.001
12	70 ± 6.0	77 ± 6.6	0.001
14	69 ± 6.1	76 ± 6.7	0.001

Discussion

The comparative evaluation of phenylephrine and mephentermine for mitigating hemodynamic responses to oxytocin administration during elective cesarean sections under spinal anaesthesia reveals critical insights into their efficacy and safety profiles. Both agents, widely used as vasopressors, effectively maintain maternal blood pressure but exhibit distinct mechanisms and hemodynamic outcomes.

Phenylephrine, a selective α -adrenergic agonist, acts predominantly through peripheral vasoconstriction, rapidly increasing blood pressure. [1] [8] this characteristic makes it particularly effective during the early stages of spinal anaesthesia-induced hypotension, a common occurrence exacerbated by oxytocin administration. [4] In the present study, phenylephrine demonstrated a rapid onset of action, effectively preventing significant hypotensive episodes following oxytocin administration. However, its use was frequently associated with reflex bradycardia due to baroreceptor-mediated responses. [5]

This bradycardia, while generally manageable, requires vigilant monitoring and may pose challenges in patients with pre-existing cardiac conditions. Mephentermine, a mixed α and β -adrenergic agonist, offers a broader hemodynamic

effect by enhancing cardiac output and peripheral vascular resistance. [7]

The present study findings highlight mephentermine's ability to stabilise heart rate while effectively preventing hypotension. This makes it particularly advantageous in scenarios where bradycardia could compromise maternal or fetal outcomes. Although its onset of action is slower than phenylephrine, its overall cardiovascular stability ensures fewer fluctuations in maternal hemodynamic parameters.

The findings of this study align with previous research, further contextualising these agents' relative strengths and limitations. Mohta M et al. [9] conducted a randomised trial comparing phenylephrine and mephentermine in cesarean sections under spinal anaesthesia, demonstrating that both agents effectively prevented maternal hypotension.

While phenylephrine showed a higher incidence of bradycardia and reactive hypertension, mephentermine provided a more consistent cardiac output, aligning with the current observations. Despite these differences, neonatal outcomes, such as Apgar scores and umbilical pH, remained similar across groups, emphasising the safety of both vasopressors in terms of fetal well-being.

Similarly, a recent study by Senapati LK et al. [10] explored phenylephrine, norepinephrine, and

mephentermine for managing maternal hypotension. Phenylephrine was noted for its rapid action and efficacy in maintaining systolic blood pressure, yet it required more frequent rescue interventions than mephentermine.

This corroborates the present findings that phenylephrine is highly effective for immediate correction of hypotension but may necessitate more comprehensive monitoring and dose adjustments during prolonged surgical procedures. Further supporting evidence comes from studies examining phenylephrine's role in managing oxytocin-induced hypotension. Mohta M et al. [11] demonstrated that phenylephrine administered prior to oxytocin injection effectively maintained maternal blood pressure and minimised hemodynamic fluctuations. However, the dose-dependent risk of bradycardia raised concerns about its optimal dosing strategy. Duggappa D et al. [12] explored the impact of varying phenylephrine doses, concluding that higher doses were more effective in reducing hypotension but increased the likelihood of bradycardia.

These findings reinforce the need for careful titration to balance efficacy with safety. The clinical implications of these findings are significant. Phenylephrine's rapid action makes it an excellent choice for immediate correction of hypotension, particularly during the initial stages of spinal anaesthesia when hemodynamic changes are most pronounced.

However, its propensity to induce bradycardia necessitates close monitoring, particularly in patients with pre-existing cardiac vulnerabilities. With its dual adrenergic effects, Mephentermine provides a more balanced cardiovascular response, making it suitable for patients who may not tolerate the hemodynamic shifts associated with phenylephrine. Both agents have demonstrated favourable neonatal outcomes, underscoring their safety profiles when used appropriately.

This is crucial in obstetric anaesthesia, where maternal hemodynamic stability directly impacts fetal oxygenation and acid-base status. Future research could focus on combination therapies or innovative dosing regimens that leverage the strengths of both agents, optimising hemodynamic management while minimising adverse effects.

In summary, the selection of phenylephrine or mephentermine should be tailored to the clinical scenario, considering the patient's cardiovascular status and the duration of the procedure. Phenylephrine's fast action and strong vasoconstrictive properties make it suitable for immediate correction of hypotension, whereas mephentermine provides a more stable cardiovascular response, supporting consistent hemodynamic control. These findings add to the

expanding evidence base that advocate for individualised vasopressor strategies in cesarean deliveries, prioritising the best possible outcomes for both mother and baby.

Conclusion

The choice between phenylephrine and mephentermine should be individualized based on the patient's cardiovascular profile and clinical needs. Phenylephrine is recognized for its rapid action, making it highly effective for immediate management. Conversely, mephentermine offers greater hemodynamic stability but often necessitates repeated dosing. Both drugs are deemed effective and safe, supporting tailored approaches to optimize maternal and neonatal outcomes during cesarean sections. Importantly, phenylephrine generally does not require repeated administration, unlike mephentermine, where multiple doses are more frequently required.

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